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DEM Generalization Tool Using Grid-Based Quadric Error Metric

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Abstract—We introduce a novel tool for generalizing Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) using the Quadric Error Metric (QEM), specifically adapted for raster grids. While traditional QEM methods have been used for polygonal simplification, our approach applies QEM directly to raster DEMs, providing a robust solution for land surface generalization. This method enables progressive generalization through an iterative process that smooths out subtle details while preserving key landforms and geomorphic structures. The tool incorporates a sharpness parameter that allows users to fine-tune the generalization process by balancing edge preservation (or even accentuation) and simplification. The tool avoids the typical peak-clipping and valley-filling effects associated with simpler smoothing techniques, effectively maintaining the depth and height of non-generalized forms. Additionally, the approach ensures that significant surface features are preserved even at high levels of generalization. Implemented in Rust, this command-line tool provides an efficient, open-source solution for processing DEMs in geomorphometric and other geoscientific applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern mapping technologies, primarily LiDAR, enable the creation of high-precision Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) capable of capturing subtle topographic variations. While these high-resolution DEMs inherently include surface roughness and small landforms, preserving such detail is unnecessary—and often undesirable—for analyses focused on larger geomorphic structures. According [1], neither the highest resolution nor the initial data scale ensures optimal representation, emphasizing the need for scale optimization. Additionally, calculating derivatives amplifies high-frequency noise, with higher-order derivatives being nearly unusable without DEM smoothing [2]. Thus, small-scale noise is often suppressed through techniques like grid resampling, low-pass filtering, or polynomial smoothing, although these methods do not effectively preserve critical features such as ridges and valleys [3, 4]. Efforts to minimize

excessive feature smoothing have involved the implementation of variable-size filters [5] and the utilization of restricted neighborhoods [6].

Advanced methods aim to preserve key land surface features while reducing noise. Wavelet transformations, morphological operations, and drainage-preserving approaches target specific applications, but they have their own limitations [7] and require subjective parameter tuning, limiting their broader use. These methods often fail to support the high-level generalization needed to identify and analyze the major geomorphic structures bounded by distinct edges. For such cases, Triangulated Irregular Networks (TIN) based generalization methods are more effective. Various techniques, such as those by [8, 9], have been developed to generalize and reconstruct land surfaces using TINs, which involve extracting 3D points and triangulation. In other fields, numerous procedures have been developed, with the Quadric Error Metric (QEM), introduced by [10], excelling in polygonal model simplification by producing near-optimal triangles for surface representation [11].

While QEM-based TIN models perform well, their lack of smoothness complicates the calculation of some land surface parameters (LSPs) [12], and the conversion back to grids adds complexity [13]. This limitation motivated us to adapt the QEM framework for raster DEMs, offering a novel approach to land surface simplification. Unlike previous work [14], which, as known, only used QEM for grids (in basic form and not solely on the grid), our method operates directly on raster grids, utilizing the full potential of the QEM method, similar to its original application. By leveraging QEM's strengths within a grid structure, our approach introduces a new methodology for generalized DEMs that retains essential land surface features, while the spatial structure meets the requirements for many subsequent analyses. The resulting generalized gridded DEM is

primarily intended for analyzing the noise-free surface of larger landforms but can also be used, for instance, to detect the filtered signal component representing residual topography.

II. METHODS

A. Original Quadric Error Metric Approach

QEM, first introduced by [10], is a widely used method for polygonal surface simplification. It reduces mesh complexity while preserving the overall shape by quantifying the geometric error introduced during simplification. Each vertex is associated with a set of planes derived from the triangles surrounding it, capturing local surface curvature. The quadric error for a vertex is calculated as the sum of squared distances from the vertex to the planes of adjacent triangles. Vertices on the original surface have zero error. Simplification involves collapsing edges, merging incident planes, and displacing vertices, which increases the error.

QEM is compactly represented by a 4×4 symmetric matrix Q , known as the quadric matrix

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c & d \\ b & e & f & g \\ c & f & h & i \\ d & g & i & j \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The matrix Q encodes the surface characteristics and enables the calculation of vertex error and the optimal vertex position. The Q matrix can be visualized as an ellipsoidal level surface. When two vertices are contracted, their quadric matrices Q_1 and Q_2 are summed such that $Q = Q_1 + Q_2$. The resulting matrix encodes the combined surface properties, allowing efficient determination of the optimal new vertex position to minimize distortion. This approach ensures a balance between simplification and geometric fidelity.

B. Grid-Based Adjustments to the Quadric Error Metric

QEM can also be adapted for raster grid simplification, although significant modifications are necessary compared to its application to polygonal surfaces. In this adaptation, grid nodes act as vertices, with their associated planes calculated using the eight triangles formed by the node and its eight neighbors. Each node is assigned a quadric matrix Q , representing the local surface characteristics. Combining the node Q matrix with the Q matrices of neighboring nodes and calculating the new elevation constitute a generalization step.

Unlike polygonal surfaces, where vertices can be repositioned, raster grids fix the x and y coordinates, requiring only the elevation z to be optimized. The optimal z value minimizes the error function derived from Q :

$$z = -\frac{cx + fy + i}{h} \quad (2)$$

where the coefficients are derived from Q matrix (1).

Incorporating neighboring nodes' Q matrices into the calculation introduces a smoothing effect, as noted by [14]. However, they did not use the key strength of QEM, which lies in its ability to evaluate errors after simplification steps, enabling changes that minimize distortion and preserve significant features, even at high levels of generalization.

For raster grids, an effective approach involves including neighbors whose errors, relative to their ideal positions based on Q , fall below a set threshold (Fig. 1). This ensures that nodes contributing to the new Q -values belong to a similar surface shape. Nodes beyond landform edges, which are associated with higher errors, are excluded, preserving critical surface features. When iteratively repeated with progressively increasing error thresholds, this process mirrors the original QEM procedure.

III. RESULTS

A. Algorithm Implementation

Implementation of presented algorithm for grid-based QEM generalization needs to solve problem of setting suitable error threshold. Rather than using a fixed threshold, we dynamically set the threshold for each iteration based on the errors from the previous step, selecting a chosen percentile that increases from its initial value to 100 by the final iteration. This approach introduces a *sharpness* parameter (ranging from 0 to 9) to balance generalization between less complex areas (with smaller deviations) and regions with significant shape changes (with larger deviations). The initial percentile is calculated as $1 - (0.1 \times \textit{sharpness})$. Higher *sharpness* values preserve edges and pronounce shape changes but require more iterations to achieve the same level of generalization.

Figure 1. Pixel selection for QEM-based simplification. a) Low threshold: selects pixels (blue) with most similar shapes to the central pixel (purple). b) High threshold: includes more contributing pixels.

We implemented the described iterative generalization algorithm and developed the QEM Generalization, a command-line tool written in the Rust programming language. It relies on GDAL for raster handling and requires a Rust development environment for building from source. The source code, along with detailed instructions for building and usage, is available on GitHub [15]. This tool is part of the broader Physical Geomorphometry Tools project, which focuses on physically based methods for detecting and analyzing land surface structures and land surface dynamics. Its goal is to provide useful tools for processing DEMs within this framework.

B. Using the QEM Generalization Tool

One of the advantages of generalization using QEM is that it does not require advanced settings. The input to the algorithm comprises a DEM raster, the desired level of generalization (specified as the number of iterations), and a *sharpness* parameter (defaulting to 5). The output is a generalized DEM raster. Raster traversal for value calculations is parallelized, and number of used cores can be selected. Given our focus on high levels of generalization where preserving the original resolution is not critical, users have an option for resampling the data to a lower resolution.

The main generalization parameter is the number of iterations, with a higher number naturally leading to a greater level of generalization. Fig. 2 shows the incremental generalization of a detailed LiDAR DEM with increasing iterations. The algorithm progressively generalizes the surface, smoothing out subtle features while retaining essential structures. Notably, the algorithm avoids the peak-clipping and valley-filling effects typical of simple smoothing methods. It effectively preserves the depth or height of small non-generalized forms, addressing a challenge faced by many other methods. Edges are preserved based on their significance through QEM's advanced surface shape handling in the surrounding area of each pixel.

The *sharpness* parameter can be used to fine-tune the generalization. Increasing the sharpness value not only improves edge retention but can even accentuate edges. This compensates for the implicit edge smoothing caused by downsampling when it is used. On the other hand, a *sharpness* value of zero removes the use of QEM error for selecting neighbors with similar surface shapes, resulting in the uniform use of all neighboring points. The difference between the extreme values of sharpness is shown in Fig. 3.

IV. CONCLUSION

The developed tool introduces an innovative approach to generalizing DEMs by adapting the QEM for direct use with raster grids. This method effectively integrates the capabilities of QEM with the benefits of the most common grid-based structure.

Figure 2. Generalization levels: A – Input DEM, B – 20 iterations, C – 100 iterations, D – 500 iterations. Contour interval: 10 m. Site: Mlynská dolina, Lúčanská Fatra, Slovakia.

Figure 3. Different *sharpness* settings: A – *sharpness* = 0, B – *sharpness* = 9. Generalized with 100 iterations. Contour interval: 10 m. Site: Piatrová, Lúčanská Fatra, Slovakia.

A major strength of the tool is its ability to retain edges, significant landforms, and maintain the depth and height of small terrain features. Moreover, its simplicity makes it highly user-friendly, not requiring advanced input parameters for effective operation. However, the inclusion of a sharpness parameter allows users to fine-tune generalization, balancing edge preservation and the enhancement of important surface features. This versatility makes it well-suited for diverse needs, ensuring the preservation of critical structural details even under significant generalization. It provides a robust and efficient solution for processing high-resolution DEMs, serving as a valuable tool for land surface analysis, especially for the physically based digital geomorphological mapping where such generalization has a key role [16].

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